

CLINICAL MANIFESTATION OF MULTISYSTEM INFLAMMATORY SYNDROM IN CHILDREN

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Annotation. SARS-CoV-2 is a relatively new and insufficiently studied pathogen; consequently, the diseases it causes and the complications that may develop after a coronavirus infection are diverse and unpredictable, especially in children. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), over than 7 milliard people have been infected with the coronavirus to date (1). Although the majority of those infected are middle-aged and elderly individuals, a significant number of children are also affected.

While at the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic, it was widely believed that this disease usually progresses asymptotically in children and very rarely leads to fatal outcomes (2), one of the known complications of the post-COVID state is the so-called "Post-COVID Multisystem inflammatory Syndrome in Children (MIS-C)" Systematic reviews by the WHO are regularly updated (3). Nevertheless, misdiagnosis and, consequently, inadequate treatment of patients with post-COVID multisystem inflammatory syndrome, discrepancies in the referral diagnosis, and its inconsistency with the clinical state of patients remain pressing issues today. The COVID-19 has been identified in residents of Uzbekistan. Having recovered from this variant of infection, the children were observed to have post-covid syndrome, in particularly, MIS-C. As regard rheumatic disease (collagenoses), they were characterized various clinical manifestation and clinical courses.

MIS-C was characterized smaller virus stress than critical course of COVID-19 (4).

Keywords: SARS-CoV-2, MIS-C, post-covid complications, collagenoses, rheumatic disease.

Relevance. The COVID-19 has been identified in residents of Uzbekistan. Having recovered from this variant of infection, the children were observed to have post-covid syndrome, in particularly, MIS-C [1,3,5,7]. As regard rheumatic disease (collagenoses), they were characterized various clinical manifestation and clinical courses. Research in recent years indicates a significant change in the clinical course of the disease and an increase in the number of cases of MIS-C was characterized smaller virus stress than critical course of COVID-19 [1,2,4,6].

Despite a large number of studies concerning various aspects of post-covid complications in childhood and updating of foreign guidelines for the management of collagenoses in children many issues remain controversial and require solutions.

The aim of the study was to study the features of the course of post-covid syndrome in children after COVID-19 infection, in particularly, with the rheumatic disease.

Material and methods. In total, 20 patients who had SARS-CoV-2 infection were examined in a Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institution's clinic (TashPMI). Control were assembled equal patients which have not post-covid complications and less level of IgG.

Results. In examining the data of these patients, it was found that, on average, 39% of the patients with post-COVID multisystem inflammatory syndrome were girls, and 61% were boys. The average age of the patients was 8-9 years, with the oldest patient being 16 years old and the youngest 7 months old. In 28% of cases, the children had concomitant anemia. In 67% of cases, the initial symptoms included a fever accompanied by fatigue and loss of appetite. Although 12

patients were hospitalized with complaints of joint pain and swelling, only two exhibited signs of osteoporosis. Seventeen percent of patients presented with carditis, 17% with chronic tonsillitis, and 17% with community-acquired pneumonia. All patients had elevated levels of IgG, with the highest level recorded at 30 IU/mL.

Fig 1. Level of Ig G in children.

The average erythrocyte count ranged from 3.83 to $3.86 \cdot 10^{12}/L$, with lowest at $2.74 \cdot 10^{12}/L$. Hemoglobin levels ranged between 75 and 162 g/L, with an average of 103 g/L. Consequently, the average color index was 0.8.

Fig 2. Erythrocyte and hemoglobin in children with MIS-C

It was found that all patients with concomitant anemia had a low color index of 0.7. Neutrophils (segmented) averaged $53-55 \cdot 10^9/L$, with the highest level at $78 \cdot 10^9/L$ and the lowest at $38 \cdot 10^9/L$. Considering the age of the patients, most had neutrophil levels within the

normal range, with no left shift detected. Lymphocyte levels were elevated considering the patients' ages, with the highest level recorded at $57 \times 10^9/L$ in a fourteen-year-old patient, and the lowest at $20 \times 10^9/L$ in a six-year-old patient. Additionally, 67% of patients had elevated monocyte levels ($3-5 \times 10^9/L$). The erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR) was also elevated in 22% of patients, while 67% had ESR levels at the upper limit of normal (7-8 mm). The highest ESR recorded was 21 mm.

All patients had low calcium levels (89%). Other biochemical indicators were within normal ranges. In the rheumatologic panel, elevated levels of C-reactive protein (CRP) were noted in 39% of patients, and elevated levels of antistreptolysin O (ASLO) were observed in 44% of patients. Instrumental examinations revealed reactive changes in the liver in 33% of patients, in the kidneys in 11%, incomplete bundle branch block in 44%, and repolarization disorders in 11%. Radiological examinations indicated osteoporosis in 11% of the cases.

Conclusion. The analysis of studies showed a post-Covid multisystem inflammatory syndrome that can simulate the clinical picture of JRA and SLE in children. Positive ICL IgG COVID-19 and rheumatological tests make it possible to diagnose PIMS with COVID-19 instead of similar collagenosis and, accordingly, prescribe adequate therapy.

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